

How do IoT solutions enable circular economy business models?

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Abstract

The transition from linear economy to circular economy (CE) business models represents a paradigm shift towards sustainability, including resource and material efficiency, reduced negative environmental impacts and minimised leakages from a circular system. The current twin transition refers to green transition (sustainability) and digital transition (digitalisation). In the manufacturing industry, the Internet of Things (IoT) emerges as a catalyst in this transformation, offering connectivity and real-time data and enabling improved monitoring, optimisation and management of operations. Utilisation of IoT promotes implementation of circularity actions, that is, optimises resource use, extends product lifecycles and facilitates recovery and reuse of materials.

This paper explores the relation between IoT and CE business models and addresses IoT's role in enabling them. The topic is limited to the manufacturing context, excluding the business models associated with the use phase but including the earlier lifecycle phases of a product, as well as possible remanufacturing steps. The area of study is tackled by reviewing the relevant literature and mapping the connections and possibilities compatible with IoT solutions and CE business models. This research also considers practical benefits from a circularity and sustainability perspective. Based on the findings, the paper concludes that IoT technologies support different CE actions and help implement them in a smart manufacturing ecosystem. IoT solutions enable certain CE business models, especially related to material control and efficiency, while improving the overall transparency and sustainability of the value chain processes.

CCS Concepts

• General and reference; • Document types; • General conference proceedings;

Keywords

Circular economy, Internet of Things, manufacturing industry, business models, twin transition

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1 INTRODUCTION

The current production and consumption patterns are reaching the physical and material limits of the Earth. Rockström et al. [30] already defined the planetary boundaries in 2009, which encompass the safe operating space for humanity. A separate threshold was determined for each of the interconnected subsystems: climate change, biodiversity loss, nitrogen cycle and phosphorus cycle, stratospheric ozone depletion, ocean acidification, global freshwater use, land use change, atmospheric aerosol loading and chemical pollution. Three of the nine boundaries were transcended then. Fourteen years later, in 2023, six of the nine boundaries were already exceeded, and one of the remaining three was approaching the threshold [29].

The continuous increase in unsustainable production and consumption, especially in Europe, is wasteful from both environmental and economic perspectives [9]. Circular economy (CE) as a paradigm shift is driven by material scarcity, renewing traditional business models and transitioning to more sustainable production and consumption patterns. CE can be implemented in multiple phases of a value chain, including the manufacturing environment.

The manufacturing industry has been in transition towards more digitalised manufacturing operations for a while now, which can also be referred to as the Fourth Industrial Revolution or Industry 4.0. Twin transition, which is the simultaneous transition towards circular and digitalised manufacturing, transforms the traditional manufacturing industry and enables the adoption of new kinds of business models. The goal of this paper is to research how Internet of Things (IoT) solutions as part of Industry 4.0 in a manufacturing environment could be utilised since IoT has been considered one of the most essential technologies in implementing all aspects of CE [17].

The topics about combining IoT and CE have increased in popularity over the past years but still need more practical research and an in-depth investigation into specific areas of CE implementation [23]. Due to this relatively new area of study and the slower adoption of the technologies, many research papers focusing on literature reviews or systematic approaches have examined the opportunities, risks and aims to answer the question of whether the technologies support the overall CE. Alcayaga et al. [2] have noted that despite some studies on how IoT is integrated into circular services, there is still a lack of research about the technologies' impacts on circular strategies or business model components.

This paper aims to answer the "how" question while examining what practical CE actions and business models are enabled by IoT. Another goal is to review the actual sustainability impacts and possibilities that IoT facilitates through CE business models as they

are not yet studied broadly in this context. The business models and their catalysation are reviewed more generally, except for a few more precise examples found in the literature.

CE is divided into biological and technical cycles [10]. This paper focuses on the technical cycle, which is the management of physical assets and products. However, due to certain limitations, this paper provides an overview, thus only scratching the surface of the broad topic and filling the gap between IoT and CE business models, as well as examining their effects on the environment and on society in general. The paper excludes the assessment of possible drawbacks and negative impacts of the adoption of IoT systems, such as increases in both energy consumption and the amount of electronic waste.

The rest of this paper is structured as follows. Section 2 presents the research context and theoretical background of CE and IoT. Section 3 describes the methodological process employed in this study. The findings obtained from the literature, mapped with a list of circularity actions, are presented in Section 4. Finally, the discussion (section 5) and the conclusions (section 6) explore the topic in more depth, reflecting the study's results and contributions to the manufacturing industry.

2 BACKGROUND

To create a solid foundation for the study presented in this paper, the following subchapters introduce the topics of CE and CE business models, Industry 4.0 and IoT and, finally, digitalised CE and the role of IoT in it.

2.1 CE and Circular Business models

CE is an emerging regenerative system, intended to quietly replace the traditional linear economy. In linear economy, the resources are typically extracted from virgin raw materials or other non-renewable or non-recycled sources. The production and manufacturing process simply serves one function, and material or other resource leakages can occur. The product is disposed after its use due to product quality or it is no longer needed. CE presents a contrast, wherein the materials are in a closed loop, aiming to eliminate excess material inputs and leakages [11]. The Ellen MacArthur Foundation [10] has set three principles for CE and primary and secondary metrics to evaluate and measure them. The principles are 1) preserving and enhancing natural capital and balancing renewable flows; 2) optimising and circulating products, components and materials in both technical and biological cycles; and 3) fostering system effectiveness while minimising negative externalities.

The objectives behind CE are more related to material use, waste reduction and the economic aspect of sustainability instead of focusing on overall sustainability. The main goals of CE are to use resources more efficiently and reduce carbon dioxide (CO₂) emissions through circularity actions. However, Korhonen et al. [15] have suggested that successful CE should take all sustainability dimensions (ecological, economic and social) into account. CE has some constraints; for example, some circulation loops might result in producing more emissions than virgin material extraction would. In such cases, a more pragmatic approach could be taken, and, if necessary, other aspects could be considered and prioritised [11]. Some rebound effects could also occur; for instance, efficient

production would decrease the prices of goods, leading to even higher consumption. Another example of a rebound effect is path dependency from reduced material supplies due to the use of waste as raw material or an energy source [15].

Circularity includes designing a product or a service in a way that the production or process utilises as few virgin materials as possible, and its lifecycle could be extended compared to its conventional equivalent. The practical implication is to extend the product lifecycle actions, such as maintenance, reuse and recycling, that prolong the use of the product or the material [11]. The actions taken through a product lifecycle-enabling circularity can be referred to as R-cycles or R-strategies, which are refuse, rethink, reduce, reuse, repair, refurbish, remanufacture, repurpose, recycle and recover [25].

The CE business models create value from implementing different CE actions, usually beyond production phases, while improving resource efficiency and extending the product lifecycle [19, 24]. The models capture revenues or other business value beyond the traditional take-make-waste linear economy, which is the business-as-usual strategy. The business models in the context of the manufacturing industry are more focused on the earlier lifecycle phases and the phases where the manufacturing context is relevant, such as remanufacturing.

The Ellen MacArthur Foundation [9] has created the ReSOLVE framework, comprising six CE business-related actions – regenerate, share, optimise, loop, virtualise and exchange – based on the three circularity principles. The research work behind this paper utilises this framework as a guide. The business models studied in this paper have been grouped under the framework's six actions to help map the benefits of IoT under different business model types.

CE business models can also be divided based on narrowing, slowing and closing the loop [4]. Narrowing the loop aims for resource efficiency and the reduction of the needed resource flows. Slowing the loop means extending the product lifecycle, which is typically enabled by a circular design. Closing the loop involves the circular flow of materials, executed through recycling, where the loop between post-use and production is closed.

Recycle and redesign are the core elements used to link upstream and downstream circular strategies, so their linkage is necessary for extending the product lifecycle and shifting resource use towards recycled and renewable materials. The performance of different circularity actions accelerates the implementation of other actions, which promotes the transition even further [8].

2.2 Internet of Things

Industry 4.0, which can also be referred to as the fourth industrial revolution, involves the integration of Cyber-Physical Systems (CPSs) into different value chain operations, especially in manufacturing and logistics. The drivers of the development of Industry 4.0 are customers' individual needs for personalised products, companies' increasing flexibility and adaptability, and requirements for energy and resource optimisation and efficiency [3].

Industry 4.0 covers technologies such as CPSs and IoT, which entail the connection of the digital and the physical worlds. The utilisation of technologies under the concept of Industry 4.0 can support the whole value chain and create a smart manufacturing

environment [3], which fulfils the requirements identified as the drivers of the change. The adoption of IoT technologies and the implementation of smart industrial ecosystems also promote collaboration along the value chain and with other companies [36].

IoT utilises different applications, such as tags, sensors, the global positioning system (GPS) and laser scanners. It connects the items with a unique Internet Protocol (IP) address for communication and information exchange [8]. IoT as a technology can be divided into multiple architectural layers. These include the perception layer with sensory capabilities, the network layer with wired and wireless communication protocols, the application layer for providing data to the end user, and the management layer [36] which enables overall management, tracking, positioning and monitoring of the items; it could also provide analysis and support decision-making [8, 36].

IoT can be applied to multiple levels, for example, to products, manufacturing machines, industrial parks or even to an entire value chain [2]. Smart manufacturing systems that have an IoT integration typically consist of the IoT-embedded machinery that collects the manufacturing-related data, as well as software systems for interpreting and analysing the collected data.

IoT can collect data on machine health, usage and fuel consumption [26], which enables optimisation of the processes and predictive maintenance of the production equipment and machines. For example, Turner et al. [35] studied and created an IoT data framework for digitalised maintenance to implement the repair and refurbishment circular strategies. The comprehensive integration pursues data-driven decision-making [14] that can be applied to the whole value chain.

IoT integration of products starts in the manufacturing phase where the sensors and smart chips are embedded in the products [21]. IoT technologies can be utilised in unique products' passports or material passports to collect data and provide useful information, especially in the recycling phase [2]. Unique item-level identification and tracking can be executed, for example, via SmartTags, which detect the environmental parameters of the products' transport and surroundings [12].

IoT provides information on a product's real-time location, composition, condition and lifecycle data, which can be used for product development. Real-time remote monitoring and data supply enable control and optimisation of the whole supply chain, including manufacturing, logistics, route planning and waste management [8, 22, 36].

Machinery and metals, chemicals, construction and electronics are industries that often already utilise IoT applications in their operations and management, especially in production and supply chain data acquisition [34]. IoT and the continuous data flow can be regarded as prerequisites for the adoption of more advanced digital technologies, which may have led to the broader utilisation of IoT [34].

2.3 Digitalised CE

Traditionally, CE business models are viewed as costly and resource-requiring processes due the management of data, tracking and tracing and information security. Overall, digital technologies help

overcome such barriers because they make the process more efficient and optimised and enable collaboration along the value chain, which accelerate the adoption of circular business models even further and make them more appealing [7]. Digital technologies create the possibility to connect different actors along the value chain, such as organisations' suppliers and customers. Digital technologies promote the transition towards services instead of physical products while collecting useful data related to the usage of both products and services [20].

CE and supply chain resilience as part of new sustainability requirements can be improved through the redesign of the value chain, for which different digital technologies are beneficial [7]. Practices that can be implemented through digitalisation that enhances CE include design and simulation, optimisation, tracking and tracing [7] which can even be conducted remotely [22]. IoT affects CE and its business models often in multiple ways, making overall improvements without an intentional target since it is an integrable technology that can be adopted at different levels and in various operations [31]. Big Data analysis and data interpretation capabilities affect how well IoT is harnessed for the implementation of circular strategies and business models.

Leminen et al. [18] assume that the emerging business models will be the main vehicles of IoT business models and ecosystem creation. They suggest that an emerging IoT ecosystem and a trusted collaborative work ecosystem require business partnership and collaboration [27]. The same principle can be applied to a broader context, integrating both CE and IoT business model development in a collaborative business environment.

In the context of business model innovation and creation, digital technologies support the implementation of CE and its management and improve the overall performance of business models [26]. Business models influence different stakeholders, and some researchers suggest that the knowledge and skills of suppliers and producers be developed [13]. In some business models that involve cooperation with consumers, the latter influence how well the model is adopted and implemented in the long term if customers are part of the ensemble.

Platform-based economies and Product–Service System (PSS) models have naturally co-evolved with digitalisation [2]. Digital technologies, including IoT solutions, are more often integrated in later lifecycle phases or are already used in some circular business models, such as the mentioned PSS models and service-based models [1, 31]. The PSS and the use phase-related models mainly contribute to the R-strategies of reuse and repair.

IoT enables continuous data collection that benefits business strategies and lifecycle management overall. For example, the data collection from the product use and end-of-life phases helps in designing and improving a product to match user needs and enable the lifecycle extension through different R-strategies, such as remanufacture, recycling and recovery [7]. IoT helps in the execution of circularity and sustainability operations, such as resource management [31] considering material and waste flows and volumes, and in optimising R-strategies. IoT enables route optimisation, which results in lower CO₂ emissions from transportation. Value chain actors' monitoring and tracking foster the reduction of negative environmental impacts and improve the efficiency of the entire value chain [7, 22].

For lifecycle management and smart maintenance and repair options, IoT-embedded devices can be connected to a decision support system that collects and analyses real-time data [21]. It supports decisions related to the maintenance and replacement of product components, which promotes the circularity action and thus the usage phase of a product [2].

The collection of maintenance history data makes it possible to create a maintenance plan that leads to higher servitisation levels [2] often desired in CE business models. Smart maintenance can be divided into three categories: condition-based (monitoring), predictive (data analysis and behaviour prediction) and prescriptive maintenance (a product autonomously detects possible maintenance needs and can make a self-diagnosis) [2].

3 METHODOLOGY

A literature review was the main method employed to investigate the research topics. The materials used were journal articles related to the topics of IoT in an industrial context and IoT for CE and different sustainability actions. The CE business models were also explored and classified as a separate topic to create a foundation for what possible CE business models could be implemented in the manufacturing context. Business models were selected based on their primary impacts and where in the lifecycle the core element of the business model took place. As this paper examines the manufacturing context of circularity, some business models that are fully based on third-party service providers or recycling strategies are excluded. In this sense, the most relevant CE business models that are selected in this paper are more related to the earlier lifecycle stages than to the later ones of a production's value chain.

To support the literature review and offer practical insights into the topics under study, this paper utilises a circularity action list, whose items were collected from the CE maturity interviews conducted under the Open Smart Manufacturing Ecosystem project. The CE maturity matrix assesses the manufacturing companies' respective stages of development via the levels of progress (linearity, industrial CE piloting, systemic resource management, CE thinking and circularity) and linear manufacturing value chain phases [32]. The data on the companies' circularity actions were gathered to justify each company's assigned level in the matrix [33]. The list has excluded some irrelevant actions that are not supporting the selected CE business models or are outside of the scope of manufacturing ecosystem.

The result of the mapping is a collection of business models that can be supported with the help of IoT solutions. The mapping is done based on findings in literature, with some applications based on theoretical knowledge. The business models are divided into categories based on which ReSOLVE action the business model contributes to. The core principle of each circularity action has affected to which business model it is allocated to. The findings from the IoT-related literature in the sustainability and circularity context is linked to similar circularity actions and business models. The Figure 1 illustrates the research process, where the data from CE maturity matrix interviews, knowledge from CE business model literature and findings from sustainability-related IoT literature are combined. The outcome of the research process is a collection of

Figure 1: Illustrated methodology and the research process.

circular business models that are supported by IoT technologies and IoT-enabled data.

4 RESULTS

There is no clear division between the business models as they can overlap. Multiple models can occur in the same product value chain, which is optimal since the business models are implemented in multiple lifecycle and production phases. This section presents the research results and possible applications of IoT. Table 1 presents the mapping, which summarises the outcome of the literature-oriented research in a table format.

The business models were mapped under the ReSOLVE framework's business actions. Therefore, the results of the mapping are explained in rows in Table 1, divided into categories based on the ReSOLVE framework. The mapping in the table combines all three main aspects of this study: CE actions, business models and IoT solutions. Based on the table, most of the selected business models are directly or indirectly enabled by IoT or benefit from such technology. However, not all of the circularity actions may benefit from IoT applications, or IoT cannot be applied to them due to their nature.

In the regenerate business model, the data provided via IoT could adjust the CE practices and the overall design, production and supply decisions [8]. It could be used to reduce unnecessary resource consumption and even assess the implementation of circular design strategies and the sustainability impacts. The relevant circular business model under the regenerate category involves circular suppliers that focus on utilising renewable energy and flows of materials that are recycled or recyclable or from other material loops [24].

Similar to sustainable procurement, circular procurement can be defined as purchases of CE products and services or considered as a purchasing tool to achieve circular production [27]. Circular procurement benefits from the automated data collection and transmission that create continuous data flow and help interconnect different organisations. The roles of IoT are to support the supplier selection based on pricing and materials, forecast the production demand, improve resource allocation and inventory visibility and help businesses manage sustainable supplier relationships [27].

In addition to implementing the circular supplies model in the material extraction lifecycle phase, another relevant aspect involves

assessment and validation of information. It includes impact assessment from product sustainability and circularity, where IoT can be utilised for developing the assessment methods.

As mentioned, business models, where conventional products are replaced with service or **sharing** platforms, have co-evolved with the development of digital technologies [2]. The business models associated with the sharing models in the framework are related to the use phase. The business models that are identified as relevant in this category are PSS and the long product lifecycle model because they can be closely connected to the manufacturer or a service provider. In the long product lifecycle model, the outcome is a durable product that is already enabled in the design and manufacturing phase (i.e., ecodesign principles are applied). It can include customer service or other helpful services for its lifecycle extension [4].

The use phase-associated IoT applications are monitoring and tracking. The collected data can be used for improving future products in terms of durability, repairability, manufacturability and reusability strategies. However, IoT seems to be more applicable in PSS and in models that already utilise digital technologies, but it does not exclude the possibility of utilising IoT in the manufacturing of products that will later be part of the long product lifecycle model. Companies can provide households with kits that connect devices to the internet and collect useful data for the product users, as well as for the companies to enable them to improve each product and its design based on the gathered data [5].

The **optimise** model includes the most circularity actions and business models that can benefit from the use of IoT. Overall, the utilisation of IoT brings energy and material savings and can be employed to monitor and optimise storage and product flows [8]. Machine monitoring can help identify possible malfunctions or errors in manufacturing, which aids in preventing waste generation from failures [20]. In logistics and transportation, IoT can optimise the usage of routes and vehicles. Routing strategies and transportation infrastructure could be improved with the help of data collection and monitoring of fuel consumption, CO₂ emissions and mileage [27].

Industrial symbiosis, which is a process-oriented solution where the waste outputs of a process are turned into inputs for another process in another value chain or manufacturing process [4]. It reduces the need for and reliance on virgin raw materials. Overall, digital technologies support the implementation of this model by monitoring the material flows and each one's type, quantity and timing. IoT increases the accuracy of information through sensors and data collection. The industrial symbiosis model can result in discovering different waste-to-resource matches and eco-networks, especially when combined with information flows from other manufacturing facilities.

Other business models that are identified as relevant in this context and based on the mapping are those used for outsourcing, producing on demand and reducing waste. The encourage sufficiency model is also included in the list, while the IoT applications are rather indirect and the model itself does not necessarily use IoT. The main purpose of the model is to promote lesser consumption and long-lasting products [4]. However, the actions are enabled by IoT, and it could also be combined with several PSS models.

The **loop** model promotes closed material circulation [9], physical assets and products in this context. The business models under this category include remanufacturing, returning and closing the loop model, which entails recovering the used materials and turning them into raw materials for other processes.

Remanufacturing practices require a lot of data related to product design, maintenance and disassembly and reassembly information [2], as well as the estimation of the residual value [28]. Data utilisation also improves the remanufactured products' predictability, process efficiency, tracking accuracy and sorting possibilities, which promote data-driven decision-making as well [2, 28].

Business models that concentrate on returning materials to their sources and closing the loop have similarities as they both contribute to sending materials back to circulation. IoT data also support practices such as reverse logistics that are relevant to the mentioned business models. In this context, the approach refers to utilising the data to close the loop through recovery, recycling and connecting the already used material to the beginning of a new product. It not only makes the model more optimal and cost-efficient but also reduces the negative environmental impact [6]. The products and packaging can be traced with sensors, Radio-Frequency Identification (RFID), barcodes or tags, such as SmartTags [12]. IoT is beneficial especially to manufacturers under an extended producer responsibility (EPR) as it helps in tracing and identifying the products sold by an original equipment manufacturer (OEM) [16].

The **virtualise** model is developed together with the digitalisation level, similar to many sharing and service-based business models that rely on different software and applications. In this context, virtualisation creates transparency in the whole value chain and provides customer support in terms of information and maintenance. From the dematerialised services, the applications or other information provided to the customer do not necessarily benefit from the use of IoT. Meanwhile, maintenance services offered by the manufacturer can interact with the product and, when combined with other digital technologies, lead to smart maintenance practices.

Virtualise and **exchange** models both typically require investing in extra technologies alongside IoT [8]. However, the utilisation of IoT creates a solid foundation for them; depending on the industry, the adoption of IoT technologies can be considered an exchange model. Often, the exchange model combines the utilisation of multiple digital technologies [20]. Due to the complex nature of this model, there are no practical examples or circularity action under this category.

Exchange models can include additive manufacturing in which IoT and data are used to manufacture customised products with 3D printers or other equipment [8, 20]. Additive manufacturing promotes multiple circularity principles since it reduces the amounts of used materials [20] and other resources and it is customised. Therefore, it will have a high probability of satisfying customer needs and can be combined with on-demand production practices.

The business models and IoT applications are mapped in Table 1. It lists the CE actions obtained from the circularity matrix described in the methodology and groups them under the ReSOLVE framework and the CE business models. The actions that can be supported with IoT technologies and subsequently applied to enable and develop different circular business models are marked X

Table 1: CE actions and mapping with compatible IoT solutions and circular business models. The first column presents all of the circular business models under the ReSOLVE framework, and the business models found in the literature are listed in the second column. The fourth column indicates whether each circularity action and the business model under which it is categorised are enabled by IoT directly (X) or indirectly (X in parentheses). The fifth column addresses the IoT application and sustainability benefits.

ReSOLVE	CE business model	CE actions	IoT	IoT application and sustainability benefits
Regenerate	Circular supplies	Certified subcontractors		
		Collecting data on materials, workforce and sites and providing visibility	x	Data provided via IoT improves the overall design [8], circular procurement and supply decisions [27] and production including the machine monitoring [20].
Share	Long product lifecycle Product-Service Systems (PSS)	Environmental and social impact assessments of suppliers	(x)	IoT-enabled data can be utilised for conducting the impact assessments.
		Ecodesign principles	x	Utilising the collected life cycle data to improve the product design to last longer [5].
		Piloting product management system to enable reuse of products	(x)	IoT data can be applied to decision-support and management systems [21].
Optimise	Encourage sufficiency Industrial symbiosis Outsourcing	Product-as-a-service business model	x	Products are shared or reused via IoT applicable platform [1, 31].
		Reuse of products, side flows and waste	x	Lesser consumption and long-lasting products, which are result of IoT enabled actions [4].
		Minimising waste with partners	(x)	Collaboration that leads to optimised use of material flows and creation of waste-to-resource matches [4].
Optimise	Produce on demand Waste reduction	Minimised transportation or local value chains	x	IoT monitoring can be applied in transportation to optimise the routes and reduce emissions [7, 22].
		Sustainable transportation options	(x)	IoT-enabled data collection can support decision-making related to transportation.
		Recycling either internally or relying on external partners	(x)	
		On-demand production and customisation of products to align with customers' needs	x	Can be implemented by analysing IoT-enabled data.
		Sustainable packaging with minimum waste		
Loop	Remanufacture Return	Monitoring of energy consumption	x	Utilisation of IoT technologies enables monitoring of energy and fuel consumption [8, 26], which can lead to more efficient reduction of them.
		Monitoring of environmental impacts	x	Monitoring material and product flows by utilising IoT [8] while reducing the negative environmental impact by analysing the data and applying necessary changes.
		Reselling of remanufactured products	(x)	Utilising IoT-enabled data improves the remanufactured products' process efficiency and tracking accuracy [2, 28].
		Reverse logistics to organise return flow	x	Manufacturers under EPR can utilise IoT to track the products and packaging after its use [6, 16]
Virtualise	Closing the loop Dematerialised services	Returning product on the end-of-life threshold via reuse, refurbishment or repurpose strategy	(x)	Tracking and returning product via IoT-enabled data collection.
		Sourcing raw materials from products at end-of-life phase	(x)	Can be connected to the circular suppliers model.
		Maintenance service	x	IoT data helps to create maintenance plans and increases servitisation level [2].
		Providing consumer applications to enable consumers to maintain product quality		

		Transparent supply chain		
Exchange	New technologies		x	All the data that is collected and used for improving the overall value chain of the product increases the transparency and virtualises the lifecycle management.
			(x)	The model includes the adoption of different novel technologies such as additive manufacturing. In some cases the adoption of IoT itself can be considered as New Technologies model [20].

or (X) in the fourth column of Table 1; X indicates that the action is applied with IoT, whereas (X) denotes indirect connections with possible IoT applications. If the cell is empty, it means that no clear connections or examples are found. The fifth column showcases the IoT application and addresses the sustainability benefits that occurs from implementing IoT. As shown in Table 1, IoT technologies may be applied to some circularity actions under the ReSOLVE framework or a certain business model but not to all of them.

5 DISCUSSION

IoT and utilisation of IoT data enable multiple circular business models. Some circular business models are excluded because the chosen context for this research is industrial, focused on manufacturing-related aspects such as raw material extraction and remanufacturing possibilities. The main contributions of IoT technologies are monitoring, optimisation, tracking and the overall data collection from the mentioned activities. IoT technologies could directly or indirectly benefit all of the studied circular business models, which are circular supplies, long product lifecycle, PSSs, encouraging sufficiency, industrial symbiosis, outsourcing, production on demand, waste reduction, remanufacturing, return, closing the loop, dematerialised services and new technologies.

The implemented circularity actions that are enabled by the use of IoT contribute to CE and overall sustainability. The main contributions belong to the ecological pillar of sustainability. Different circular business models have varying outcomes in terms of sustainability impacts. In terms of CE, there are incremental improvements that narrow and slow down the loop and radical improvements that close the loop [26].

The business models under the regenerate action support rethinking strategies and circular procurement decisions, in which the origins of the materials and the sustainability impacts of the suppliers are assessed. The actions in these models could use the data from other lifecycle phases and utilise the collected information to rethink and improve the whole value chain.

The sharing economy models are mainly focused on keeping the products themselves in circulation, with the support of digital platform-based applications. Sustainability and a circularity-oriented design ensure long-lasting products that can be reused and repaired when needed. The models are slightly in the grey area of relevance in this context since most of the platform-based PSS models are provided by third parties and the manufacturers cannot affect the circulation of the products after these have reached the customers.

The optimisation models have the most potential for adopting IoT to implement different circularity actions. The R-strategies are mainly related to reducing and reusing materials, but there is also a

model for manufacturing based on the current need, which implements the R-strategy of refusing unnecessary production. Improvements in terms of sustainability include cost savings from material tracking and reducing surplus production and waste. Higher quality and improved maintenance possibilities result in long-lasting products, in turn decreasing the need for producing new ones. Optimisation of factory environments especially contributes to CO₂ emission reductions. Monitoring also enables accurate calculations and assessment of sustainability impacts.

Loop models aim to keep products or product parts in circulation because these models focus on later lifecycle phases, including remanufacturing possibilities, returning and closing the loop. Practical actions can be reverse logistics and sourcing of recycled materials. Remanufacturing strategies especially support the definition of a successful CE proposed by Korhonen et al. [15] since the use of such strategies also enhances the social sustainability aspects, avoiding the necessity of raw material extraction, which usually has adverse effects on social sustainability, depending on the field and type of product. Loop models are strongly linked to end-of-life activities, which are outside the scope of this study but still relevant to acknowledge.

Virtualise models conventionally turn physical products into their virtual or digital equivalents. In the context of the manufacturing industry, such models include virtualising maintenance services and providing transparency. The practical sustainability benefits of smarter maintenance practices enabled by IoT are increased availability and quality of products and reduced costs and waste [2].

In the manufacturing context, relevant examples that would utilise only IoT to implement circular exchange models have not been found. In some cases, the adoption of IoT technologies can be viewed as the exchange model itself since for some companies, IoT is a relatively new technology and therefore a leap to digitalised CE. However, typically, IoT implementation in the context of adopting new technologies includes additional digital solutions, such as 3D printing in additive manufacturing. Adopting them with IoT reduces the need for materials and can increase the use of recycled materials [20].

Some researchers suggest that companies aiming towards more digital and circular businesses they first have to choose the circularity targets or an approach from the ReSOLVE framework [20, 31]. In this context, the targets could be related to the manufacturing efficiency and circulation of a specific product, including remanufacturing possibilities. After setting the targets, it is recommended that companies identify and harness the most suitable technologies to support the circularity actions [31] and eventually improve the entire business model. The success of the adoption can be measured with performance indicators and smaller targets [20].

Ranta et al. [26] argue that radical business model innovation and practices are necessary for transitioning towards circularity and truly narrowing and closing the loops. They also propose investing in data integration and analysis technologies to improve the overall adoption of IoT and to benefit from its full potential to be implemented in all circular strategies.

6 CONCLUSIONS

Decoupling excess material use from business model development is necessary in order to stay within the Earth's physical and material limits. Twin transition, which is the simultaneous transition to digitalisation and sustainability, can be viewed as a natural solution to broad sustainability issues and challenges. Twin transition can be applied in the CE context. In this case, the CE business models are combined with the utilisation of IoT. The outcome of this research is mapping, from which it can be concluded that all of the studied business models can benefit from the utilisation of IoT, directly or indirectly. The business models can be implemented in multiple phases in the same value chain and can contribute to different aspects of sustainability and CE.

IoT solutions can be applied to multiple levels, but applications in products and in the manufacturing environment are the most relevant in this context. The main benefits of IoT technologies are the transparency of the value chain and production, as well as monitoring and tracking, which enable optimisation of different processes. Optimisation results in decreased emissions, material use and waste and increased savings and efficiency. IoT can also be employed for the management of sustainable supplier relationships, the discovery of different waste-to-resource matches, reverse logistics, smart maintenance, remanufacturing and identification of possible malfunctions or errors in manufacturing and operations along the value chain. All of the collected data can be used for product improvements in terms of durability, reparability, manufacturability and reusability, which all contribute to sustainable designs, creating long-lasting products.

Future research should be more focused on practical applications since there are many existing literature reviews and systematic theoretical approaches used in the manufacturing context. Earlier lifecycle phases, including material extraction and manufacturing, have been selected as focal points in this study but require further research as well. The future research could explore the benefits and possibilities of utilising IoT technologies as a support for implementing a Digital Product Passport (DPP).

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